

Complex conductivity in heterogeneous media, can we use simple mixing laws on SIP spectra?

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Workshop session: “Tackling ambiguity: Towards a more reliable interpretation of IP signals”

Is the first and presenting author a student? No

Tackling heterogeneity? Let’s mix!

An old say in French is “C'est dans les vieux pots que l'on fait la meilleure soupe” (i.e., best soups are made in old pots) and, in this contribution, we decided to try the old cuisine of mixing laws to tackle geometrical heterogeneities. Analogous circuits in parallel and series are indeed very effective to obtain various equivalent properties (see the example of equivalent hydraulic conductivity in Renard and de Marsily, 1997). But what about complex properties such as the frequency dependent electrical conductivity that one measures with Spectral Induced Polarization (SIP)?

In this contribution we decided to test the effectiveness of three mixing laws through a series of experiments on synthetic samples made of well-characterize clay material.

Synthetic clay sample geometries and complex conductivity

In order to test the ability of mixing laws to provide accurate equivalent complex conductivity, we proposed an experimental set-up containing meso-scale heterogeneities. In this study, meso-scale refers to an intermediate scale that is larger than the pore scale and smaller than the measurements scale footprint (i.e., related to the electrode spacing in SIP, see Jougnot, 2020).

In this study, we used two types of clay material characterized previously by Mendieta et al. (2021), a red montmorillonite and an illite. Figure 1a, b, c, and d present the different geometries created to test different mixing laws using the sample holder presented in Fig. 1e: (a) perfectly mixed montmorillonite and illite, (b) organized in series, (c) and (d) organized in parallel with Illite on the top or montmorillonite on the top, respectively. Measurements were conducted with the SIP Fuchs III from 1 mHz to 20 kHz with the current injected between C1 and C2 and the potential measured in P1 and P2 (Fig. 1e). These measurements later compared to three classical mixing laws, the so-called Wiener bounds, i.e., the model in parallel (Reuss, 1929) and the model in series (Voigt, 1910), and the self-consistent approach proposed by Hashin (1968).

Table 1: Classical mixing laws to test and compare to the experimental data (Figure 1f and g)

In parallel (Reuss, 1929)	In series (Voigt, 1910)	Self-consistent (Hashin, 1968)
$\sigma_R^* = \left(\frac{c}{\sigma_1^*} + \frac{1-c}{\sigma_2^*} \right)^{-1}$	$\sigma_V^* = c\sigma_1^* + (1-c)\sigma_2^*$	$\sigma_{SC}^* = \sigma_2^* + \frac{3c\sigma_2^*}{3\sigma_2^* + (1-c)(\sigma_1^* - \sigma_2^*)}(\sigma_1^* - \sigma_2^*)$

Where σ^* is the complex conductivity of the material 1 (illite) and 2 (montmorillonite), and c ($c = 0.5$) is the volumetric proportion of material 1 with respect to the whole volume.

Figure 1: Heterogeneous samples made of montmorillonite and illite: (a) well-mixed, (b) in serie, (c) and (d) in parallel. (e) Sample holder for SIP measurements. (f) and (g) experimental results and the corresponding mixture law models for the real and the imaginary part of the complex electrical conductivity (modified from Mendieta et al., 2023).

The results of the SIP measurements of the homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures are presented in Fig. 1f and g. First, as expected, one can clearly see that the equivalent complex conductivity measured on the composite samples are distributed in between the two individual clay types, illite and montmorillonite.

Figures 1f and g also clearly show that the mixture law prediction from Table 1 compare really favorably with our experimental results (for the real and imaginary part). The only unexpected exception is for the sample in parallel with the illite placed on top (light blue line in Fig. 1f and g).

This work showed that the mixing laws are effective to provide equivalent complex conductivity for heterogeneous media. Since many natural media are organized in layers, this opens up a way to improve or simplify IP modelling for various applications from reservoir properties to Critical Zone studies.

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